

The Influence of Social Media on Moral Values and Group Norms among Secondary School Students A Study of Delta State

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ABSTRACT: This study examines the influence of social media on moral values and group norms among secondary school students in a study of the delta state. The paper covers the extent to which social media is used by secondary school students; the reasons why secondary school students use social media and the moral values and group norms that resulted from the usage of social media among secondary school students in Delta State. The descriptive research method was adopted using the quantitative approach. A total of 250 respondents were selected using the multi-stage method of sampling techniques. Data were collected with a structured questionnaire and frequency count and percentage were used to analyse the data. Thereafter, the paper concluded that secondary school students in Delta State recorded a high frequency of accessing social media. The time they spend on social media is an average of 5 hours daily. Secondary school students make use of all social media features to attract sexual compliments from their numerous friends (Near and distant). Social media has a significant influence on social values and group norms by way of sexual exposure on social media and they tend to display some of the content they see on social media. The recommendations for the heavy usage of social media by secondary school students in Delta State should be discouraged as their parents should ensure they monitor the contents of the social media they access. posting of sexual content on social media should be discouraged and secondary school students in Delta State should be taught how to block users who frequently nude pictures and videos parents should restructure the time at which their school children access the social media and the contents that they view, read and share.

KEYWORDS: Social Media, Moral Values, Group Norms, Students

1. INTRODUCTION

Social media have changed the way people especially young people do things. In recent times, the trend in social communication among people and organizations has changed with the advent of social media networks. Social media has contributed to the increased number of online conversations and relationship activities based on peer-to-peer points of view. The pattern of social media communication depends on the nature and features of each of the social media platforms. Internet activities engaged by younger demographics have increased in recent times. Internet platforms did not only increase communication among young people but the social interactions of people were positively affected. Breaking down the platforms through which people connect, social media is a commonly used internet connectivity platform in recent times. In further classification, Facebook, WhatsApp, Instagram and LinkedIn are dominating. According to Zarouali, Brosius, Heuberger and De-Vreese (2021), instant messaging applications such as Facebook, Messenger and WhatsApp have become important channels for private interactions with different people in society.

This is important because the definite nature of social media contributes to the usability and functionality of the media for social engagements and activities. Social media has been viewed as the most recent technological development in the history of man for communication and other social-related activities. Social media is regarded as an online network where users are connected to other users in near and far away locations around the world. The term "social media" refers to a set of social networking sites that influence users' communication activities. According to Campbell et al. (2016), social media encompasses individual social networking sites such as Facebook, Instagram, Skype, Twitter, Whatsapp, LinkedIn, YouTube, and Tik-Tok that use collective virtual applications to allow the formation, exchange, and broadcasting of online user-generated content. As a result, it's critical to investigate how social media may help promote luxury companies in this digital age.

One of the activities that are noticed on social media is the issue of social values and group norms. According to Gwenn and Katherine (2012), many individuals especially the younger generation have discovered a new path of social values on social media. This is a result of their social activities on social media. Some of these social activities have increased immoral behaviour among secondary school students. the relationship between social media and the younger generation is the immorality of content saturating on the different platforms. Immoral behaviour has pervaded the lives of many teenagers as a result of the use of social media

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platforms. These include violence, dating, sexual abuse, bullying, harassment, criminality, and cyber-gender. According to Lenhard (2017) when it comes to teen online dating, violent communication and activities and sexual abuse within dating relationships, social media is used to perpetuate this evil in society. Sexual harassment in secondary schools has increased beyond imagination because of the content young people access on social media platforms. This form of harassment is referred to by various names, including cyberbullying, social sexual sharing, cyber gender harassment, and even more explicit and derogatory terms like revenge pornography. Teens get away with posting these images because it mostly happens at night since people don't want to get caught so they usually put it up at night and then they remove it afterwards.

Statement of Problem

Social media mobile applications have become a very important aspect of young people's lives. Social media use has grown considerably in the last decade and the majority of young adults use social media daily. Davies and Cranston (2013) highlighted the myriad advantages and prospects that social media offers to young individuals, encompassing access to information, expanded social circles, honing of social skills, expression of identity, informal learning through interest-based groups, and fostering and nurturing friendships, alongside providing a source of entertainment. However, the escalating engagement of secondary school students worldwide with social media also entails various risks and repercussions. These risks encompass concerns regarding privacy, such as oversharing personal information, dissemination of false or misleading information either about themselves or others, susceptibility to online scams, and the potential for developing internet or social media addiction, all of which could detrimentally affect their social, psychological, and emotional well-being (Gwenn and Katherine, 2012).

Research Question

- What is the extent to which social media are used by secondary school students in Delta State?
- What is the reason for social media Usage by secondary school students in Delta State?
- What is the influence of social media usage by secondary school students in Delta State on social values and group norms?

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Concept of Social Media

The internet opened opportunities for online interaction. According to the opinion of Samuel (2014), the invention of the internet brought a new dimension to the media landscape. One aspect of the Internet revolution in human communication and interaction is social media. However, from existing literature, it can be concluded that there have been different understandings of social media. This could be the functionality and platform which social media possesses. Also, people have ascribed different meanings by drawing a line of similarity to social networking sites and new media. Importantly, this paper focused on the interaction objectives of social media in relationship to social values and norms. The term "social media" refers to a set of social networking sites that influence users' communication activities. According to Campbell (2016), social media encompasses individual social networking sites. There are many social media platforms open to many people across the globe. In this study, social media platforms that are commonly used in Nigeria will be the central focus of this paper.

Therefore, many Nigerians are known to frequently use Facebook, Instagram, Skype, Twitter, Whatsapp, LinkedIn, YouTube, and TikTok. These social media platforms use collective virtual applications to allow the formation, exchange, and broadcasting of online user-generated content. Voramontri and Klieb (2018), noted that Web 2.0 and user-generated content social media are described to mean internet applications. It is User Generated Content (UGC). That is, Social media can be categorized into collaborative projects, content communities (YouTube), social networking (Facebook) virtual game worlds (world of Warcraft) and Virtual social worlds (second life). According to Lavanya and Preethi (2014), social media in simple explanation is all platforms such as Facebook, Twitter, Whatsapp LinkedIn, Snapchat, YouTube, and Instagram which are used specifically for social interactions among users. These interactions cover video sharing, picture sharing, voice message sharing, checking up on friends, birthday reminders, event reminders, and memory recall among others. What this means is that much content sharing and entertainment exist on social media.

The wide consecutiveness of social media in this digital era brings about a community of friends with different backgrounds. The community is exhaustive. People from different social, religious, cultural and ethnic backgrounds meet on social media to form a new community of friends. According to Voramontri and Klieb (2018), social media are platforms that are connected to the internet which have a proliferation of user-driven web technologies such as blogs, social networks and media sharing platforms. Collectively called social media, these technologies have enabled the growth of user-generated content and encouraged global community and relationships. There are ways people use the social media. These patterns are based on the needs of the people. Each of the social media platforms has its unique features. Obalanleye (2015), emphasized that social media have been regarded as pervasive platforms used for impacting the social life of the society. With the changing nature of social relationships, people are more closely connected. Social networking on social media websites involves the use of the internet to connect users with their friends, family and acquaintances.

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Olusena et al (2014) assert that in the first instance, social media suggests that there is a process of interaction between people. The basic idea behind social media is to create mutual relationships among users. On the other hand, the term media suggests a channel through which information is passed to a large diverse audience that may not be within the same geographical area. Two or more people establish social from different local internet networks In Nigeria few social media platforms are commonly used. These are Facebook, Instagram, WhatsApp, and Twitter, (Akra and Kumar, 2017).

Usage Pattern of Social Media by Secondary School Students

Among the users of the social media platforms is the youth. Teenagers especially those in High schools these days widely use social media for different reasons and purposes. They have made this a part of their daily activities. Every webpage that allows for social interaction is considered to be a social media site. These pages include social networking pages like Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, and Myspace, gaming sites virtual worlds such as Club Penguin and Second Life, video sites such as YouTube, and blogs (Tartari, 2013). Shabir et al (2014), show that the usage of social media networking is the domain of youth. The social media referencing which is used in the research tool are Facebook, Skype, YouTube, Twitter and Myspace.

The youth are seen to get attracted to social media and they are highly influenced. Lanhart, Purcell, Smith and Zickuhr (2012) observed that almost two-thirds (63%) of all teenagers use social media to go online at least once a day. For those youths who go online, social media use is high nearly three quarters (73%) are active users of social networking sites like Facebook or Myspace, 38% share content online such as photos, videos or artwork and 14% blog. Additionally, three-quarters (75%) of teens own a cell phone, with 88% using them for text messaging, 64% to exchange pictures and 23% to access social networking sites. Tartari (2013) posits that such social media sites offer today's youth a portal for entertainment and communication. Shabir et al (2014) argue that social media use has grown since the early years of the 21st century. Social media is utilized by populations belonging to different age groups but the youth population is at the forefront of social media sites all over the world. Nnamounu (2013) aptly expressed that while the internet mainly hosts social media sites, young people constitute the biggest users. Hence, social media have become overwhelmingly common among youths in Nigeria. One major factor that gets youth attracted to social media is the socialization function of the mass media. Nche (2012) noted that akin to a wildfire spreading rapidly during the dry season, the influence of social media has permeated every corner of Nigeria, captivating a significant portion of its youth population. Social media has gained such pervasive popularity among young people that abstaining from participation in at least one social media platform has become uncommon and even considered outdated. There is high coverage of the population of the youths by social media and most of them are regularly communicating using social media platforms. Abdulahi et al (2014) explained that human beings cannot do the same thing for long. They tend to be boring, but the younger can stay long hours just on Facebook without any complaints.

Social media is now obviously a media of the youth. What comes to mind now is what teenagers are doing on social media or what activities these populations engage in. According to Abdulahiet (2014), users of social media around the world especially share personal information on Facebook. Most of the people display personal information on their profiles. As per Madden (2013), youths in the United States and globally utilize social media platforms for diverse purposes, encompassing the creation of profiles, sharing self-made videos, updating relationship statuses, expressing personal interests, and commenting on friends' posts. They also engage in the dissemination of personal information such as birthdates, email addresses, residential addresses, school affiliations, and phone numbers, along with sharing pictures and more. Additionally, they utilize social media to maintain connections with friends, expand their networks, consume various types of content (such as music videos and advertisements), peruse profiles, explore their identities, exchange instant messages or texts, and participate in group discussions.

Moreover, recent studies conducted in South Africa and Nigeria, as highlighted by Sanusi, Gambo, and Bashir (2014), reveal that teenagers utilize social media not only for personal interactions but also as a means of accessing political, social, educational, economic, and cultural information. They use these platforms to communicate with friends, access entertainment content such as movies, photos, and music, search for employment opportunities, promote their religious beliefs, and even conduct business activities.

Influence of Social Media on Values and Group Norms

Social values and group norms are very significant variables that social media have affected in recent times. According to Shabir et al (2014), social media have various impacts on secondary school students. Social media facet the student's family and school values taught by their parents and teachers. Social media might sometimes seem like just a new set of cool tools for involving young people in negative ways that affect their social, cultural, traditional and religious values. Existing literature has vividly shown that secondary school students are among the greatest users of social media sites and they personal profile, communicate, access videos, post pictures, play music and so on. Research further identified that virtually all content patterns of social media are highly toxic for social values and religious group norms. These social media contents accessed by teenagers especially those in secondary schools pose a risk to the moral behaviour of these teenagers as well as affect their sense of judgment of social values and moral conduct. According to Ceyhan (2012), parents are ambivalent about social media content, as they are aware of the potential risk it carries by

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exposing users to negative content such as pornography, violence, commercialism, cyberbullying, unsupervised social relations, and privacy and security issues. Tertari (2013), social media also threatens teenagers' moral values in such a way that their languages, dress patterns and social life activities are threats to good morals.

Another aspect of social media on teenager's behaviour is that it exposes teenagers to engage in crime and fraud. There are many cases of fake Facebook accounts to defraud other users. This is prevailing in Nigeria with young people. The digital general in Nigerians is criminals who obtain money in pretence on social media. According to Amedie (2015), the second major issue of immoral activities on social media that can influence secondary school students is criminal activities. With the rising level of social media use, malicious and irresponsible people benefit from the freedom of social media platforms to lie, scam, attack and hurt others in several ways. Many criminals have taken advantage of social media to hide their identity and commit several crimes such as cyberbullying, cyber terrorism, human trafficking, and drug dealing. The above position is evident in Nigeria with the case of one young lady, Osokun Gloria who was lured to visit unknown young men in a hotel in Lagos through social media. She was drug and killed by the young men who introduced business to her on Facebook.

The backside of social media on the behaviour of teenagers is so overwhelming. Teenagers are recently caught in the web of social media. These moral behaviours are listed below.

- **Increased Sexual Promiscuity:** Social media has contributed significantly to the rise in sexual promiscuity, with Onah and Nche (2014) remarking on the alarming moral decline in Nigeria. Traditional values have eroded, giving way to widespread immorality, particularly among the youth. Instances of sexual harassment have surged, a trend exacerbated by social media's pervasive influence. Ani (2012) observes that individuals are now measured by their number of sexual partners rather than by moral standards, leading to the normalization of pre-marital sex, homosexuality, and lesbianism among youths. The accessibility provided by social media platforms facilitates connections with individuals of the opposite sex and the sharing of explicit content, further fueling immoral behaviour.

- **Rise in Fraud and Cybercrime:** The emergence of social media has coincided with the proliferation of cybercrime, as highlighted by Onah and Nche (2014). Scammers, colloquially referred to as "yahoo-yahoo," exploit online platforms for illicit activities, ranging from hacking to fraudulent schemes. Social media offers a fertile ground for these criminals to operate, enabling the remote perpetration of crimes with impunity. The anonymity afforded by the internet amplifies their capabilities, making it imperative to address this growing threat.

- **Impact on Indecent Dressing and Sexual Harassment:** Social media exacerbates issues of indecent dressing and subsequent sexual harassment, particularly within tertiary institutions (Onah and Nche, 2014). Platforms allowing users to share photos and videos facilitate the spread of inappropriate attire, influencing impressionable youths to emulate such behaviour. The normalization of risqué images and provocative clothing perpetuates a culture of objectification and harassment, underscoring the need for responsible social media usage.

- **Erosion of the Sacredness of Human Life:** The reverence for human life and compassion for others have waned among Nigerian youth due to their preoccupation with social media (Onah and Nche, 2014). Instead of offering aid during crises, many opt to document events for online consumption, displaying a troubling disregard for human suffering. Umekachikelu (2013) observes a disturbing trend where individuals prioritize social media engagement over basic humanitarian principles, exemplified by the callous exploitation of tragic events for online attention. This callous behaviour extends to instances where social media is used to facilitate or glorify violence, highlighting the urgent need to reaffirm the sanctity of human life in all aspects of society.

Theoretical Framework

Theoretical framework is a very important aspect of research, especially in social science. Theoretical framework guides research to be generally accepted with the scope and concepts of the study. It helps to modify the standardization of research concepts. Therefore, the research will adopt two theories. Technology Accepted Model and Uses and Gratification.

Technology Accepted Theory: This theory is very significant in the explanation of the influence of social media use. First, there is a need to define the theory. In 1980, Ajzen and Fisbein established the framework for TAM which predicts and explains consumer adoption of IT to get satisfaction for essential needs and wants, (Davis, 1989). It contends that user acceptance of a novel system is decided by users' intention to use (IU), which is impacted by users' perceptions of the system's perceived usefulness (PU) and usability (UI) (PEU).

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In the context of this study, the model targets the factors influencing students' intention to use social media. The areas of this study dwell on the intention of students in secondary school. The second aspect of the model is that it reflects the perceived usefulness of social media which focuses on the motives for using social media. The third aspect of the Model is the perceived ease of use for students to post, share, comment and do different features on social media.

Uses and Gratifications Theory: This study was adopted by Uses and Gratification theory, which suggests that people actively choose their media based on their needs. In other words, people's choice of media is highly influenced by their needs and the gratifications or satisfaction they get by using these media. Five main categories of needs have been identified based on the social and psychological functions of mass media. They include cognitive, affective, personal integrative, social integrative, and escape and diversion needs. According to Ismail (2021), the uses and gratifications main idea is that people are more likely to subscribe to information that offers them the highest level of utility and benefits; while information that may not hold adequate and tangible benefits to a certain audience may not be entertained by them. Uses and gratification is an idea that media use depends on the perceived satisfaction, needs, wishes, or motives of the prospective audience member, which are derived from psychological instincts (needs) such as information, relaxation, companionship, diversion and escape.

This study adopts the Uses and Gratifications theory as a theoretical framework for the following reasons:

- It has previously been used successfully to examine the underlying reasons for media use to satisfy particular needs.
- It has previously been used successfully to understand consumers' motivations and behaviours in the use of social media and other broadcast media.

Researchers are currently using this theory to examine the extent of use, motivations, and gratifications for the exponential use of new media including social network sites (SNS).

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The survey design was employed in carrying out this research. The survey method is usually used when a researcher is interested in the attitude, perception and behaviour of people towards variables or phenomena. Furthermore, the researcher used the survey design through the administration of a questionnaire to the respondents. The researcher used this design because the design is most appropriate for the study. The population of the study covered secondary school students in Delta State. The total population of Delta State is 4, 000,000. For the population targeted the researcher limits the research sample to a manageable size of two hundred and fifty (250).

The method used to take the sample is the multi-stage. The researcher adopted the purposive sampling technique to select Delta State secondary school students and the three senatorial districts in the state. The cluster sampling was adapted to group the secondary schools in each of the senatorial districts along the various tribes in the district while the researcher randomly distributed the questionnaire to the respondents in the schools selected.

4. DATA PRESENTATION AND DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The chapter covers the presentation of data in table format, data analysis according to the findings from the fields and the discussion of findings as they relates to the results generated from the field.

Data presentation

Table 1. Gender Distribution of Respondents

Response	No of Frequency	Percentage
Male	125	50
Female	125	50
Total	250	100

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From above table one, it shows that from the total population of respondents of 125 (50%) each represent male and female respectively.

Table 2. Age Distribution of Respondents

Response	No of Frequency	Percentage
10-15	64	25.6
16-19	186	74.4
Total	250	100

Table 2 above clearly shows that respondents between 10-15 years of age bracket are 64 (25.6%) while those of 16-19 years of age bracket are 86 (74.4%).

Table 3. Type of Phone Use

Response	No of Respondent	Percentage
Smartphone	181	72
Window phone	48	19.2
Normal phone	21	9.4
Total	250	100

Table 3 shows that 181 (72%) of the respondents have smartphone. 48 (19.3%) of the respondents have window phone and 21 (9.4%) of the respondents have normal phone.

Table 4. Class Distribution of Respondents

Response	No of Frequency	Percentage
JSS	64	25.6
SSS	186	74.4
Total	250	100

Table 4 above clearly shows that respondents in JSS classes are 64 (25.6%) while those of in SSS classes are 86 (74.4%).

Table 5. Extent of Assessment by Social Media by students in secondary school

Response	No of Respondents	Percent
Always	200	80
Not always	50	20
Total	250	100

Table 5 shows that 200 (80%) of the respondents claimed that they always access the social media while 50 (20%) of the respondents claimed not always.

Table 6. Time Spent On Social Media by secondary school students

Response	No of Respondents	Percent
One hour	37	14.8
More than one hour	69	27.6
More than two hours	144	57.6
Total	250	100

Table 6 shows that 37 (14.8%) of the respondents claimed one hour as time spent on social media. 69 (27.6) claimed more than one hour and 144(57.6%) of the respondents claimed more than two hours.

Table 7. Social Media Sites Accessed by secondary school students

Response	No of Respondents	Percent
One	21	8.4
Two	70	28
Three	68	27.2
Four	91	36.4
Total	250	100

Table 7 shows that 21 (8.4%) of the respondents have one social media site they access. 70 (28%) respondents have two. 68 (27.2%) have three and 90 (36.4%) have four social media sited they access.

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Table 8. Number of Friends on Social Media

Response	No of Respondents	Percent
500	93	37.2
1000	107	42.8
2000	28	11.2
5000	22	8.8
Total	250	100

Table 8 shows that 93 (37.2%) respondents have 500 friends on social media. 107 (42.8%) respondents claimed 1000 friends. 28 (11.2%) respondents claimed 2000 and 22 (8.8%) claimed 5000 friends.

Table 9. Device Used By Teenagers to Access Social Media

Response	No of Respondents	Percent
Laptop	11	4.4
Smartphone	239	95.6
Total	250	100

Table 9 shows that 11 (4.4%) of the respondents use laptop to access the social media while 169 (95.6) use smartphones.

Table 10. Reason for Access Social Media by secondary school students

Response	No of Respondents	Percent
Socialization	210	84
News update	25	10
Academic purpose	15	6
Total	250	100

Table 10 shows that 210 (84%) of the respondents claimed that the reason for accessing social media is socialization 25 (10%) claimed news and 15 (6%) claimed academic updates.

Table 11. Content/Post Shared by secondary school students on Social Media

Response	No of Respondents	Percent
Private pictures	21	8.4
Immoral picture	114	45.6
Academic matters	30	12
Immoral video	85	34
Total	250	100

Table 11 shows that 21 (8.4%) of the respondents share private pictures and 114 (45.6%) of the respondents claimed immoral pictures while 30 (12%) of the respondents claimed academic matters and 84 (34%) of the respondents claimed immoral video.

Table 12. Friends Comment Interest in Social Media Access

Response	No of Respondents	Percent
Immoral comments	211	84.4
Moral comments	39	15.6
Total	250	100

Table 12 shows that 211 (84.4%) of the respondents agreed that comments friends of social media interest comments are immoral while 39 (15.6%) claimed moral comments

Table 13. Social Media Content Comment Most

Response	No of Respondents	Percent
Immoral Fashion	36	14.4
Immoral Movie	77	30.8
Immoral Music	56	22.4
Immoral Comedy	81	32.4
Total	250	100

Table 13 shows that 36 (14.4%) of the respondents comment on immoral fashion posts. 77 (30.8%) claimed immoral movie. 56 (22.4%) claimed immoral music and 81 (32.4%) claimed immoral comedy post.

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Table 14. Why Social Media Influence Secondary school students moral values Behaviour

Response	No of Respondents	Percent
Indecent dressing	48	19.2
Indecent language	56	22.4
Negative sexual behavior	89	35.6
Drug abuse	57	22.8
Total	250	100

Table 14 shows 48 (19.2%) of the respondents claimed that indecent dressing of social media content influence their moral values behaviors. 56 (22.4%) claimed indecent language, 89 (35.6%) claimed negative sexual behavior and 57 (22.8%) claimed drug abuse.

Table 15. Display of Immoral Behaviour by secondary school students on Social Media

Response	No of Respondents	Percent
Yes	230	92
No	20	8
Total	250	100

Table 15 shows that 230 (92%) respondents agreed that they display the behavior of people in social media while 20 (8%) disagreed.

Table 16. Negative Preference of Social Media Activities for Lifestyle

Response	No of Respondents	Percent
Yes	177	70.8
No	73	29.2
Total	250	100

Table 16 shows that 177 (70.8%) of the respondents agreed that they prefer social media activities for lifestyle while 73 (29.2%) disagreed.

DISCUSSION OF THE RESULTS

The discussion of the findings covers the major response from the respondents as it relates to the research questions.

The first findings indicated that the extent to which teens have access to social media is high with high frequency. The time they spend on social media is more than one hour on average. The findings show that they have at least two social media sites they open accounts with and this shows that they are frequently engaged in social media activities. The result shows that the average number of friends a student has on social media is seven hundred as the result shows that none of the respondents have less than five hundred friends. The respondents claimed that they access social media through their smartphones rather than laptops. According to Lavanya and Preethi (2014), social media in simple explanation is all platforms such as Facebook, Twitter, Whatsapp LinkedIn, Snapchat, YouTube, and Instagram which are used specifically for social interactions among users. These interactions cover video sharing, picture sharing, voice message sharing, checking up on friends, birthday reminders, event reminders, and memory recall among others. What this means is that much content sharing and entertainment exist on social media.

The second finding indicated that the reason why secondary school students access social media is because of socialization. The respondents affirmed that they access social media because of socialization but most time they are exposed to negative immoral content such as nude videos and pictures and their friend's content posts influence them to like social media content. Some of the contents are comedy, fashion, movies and music. The finding agreed with Lanhart, Purcell, Smith and Zickuhr (2012) who observed that almost two-thirds (63%) of all teenagers use social media to go online at least once a day. For those youths who go online, social media use is high nearly three quarters (73%) use a social networking site such as Facebook or Myspace 38% share content online such as photos, videos or artwork and 14% blog. Additionally, three quarters (75%) of all teens have a cell phone, with 88% using them to text message, 64% to exchange pictures and 23% to access social networking sites

The third result shows that respondents are sexually exposed to social media and they tend to display some of the content they see on social media. This indicated that there is a significant influence of social media on the moral values and group norms of people especially youths and school children. The finding agreed with Onah and Nche, (2014) who posited that the level of moral decadence in Nigeria has become repugnant. The previous invaluable moral values and norms have regrettably been ruined, while immorality now reigns especially among the youth. Sexual harassment has increased over the years because of social media. Also, there is a relationship between this study with Yaro (2013), who observed that the days that morality and discipline used to be virtues. This is evident in the current level of sexual promiscuity among school children especially those in secondary schools in the country. According to Ani (2012), sexual immorality has become the talk of the day in the country as one is regarded as the greatest by the number of sexual partners he/she has in the name of lovers.

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5. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

CONCLUSION

In the presentation and analysis of the data generated from the field, the researcher separated the section into bio-data and questions from the research questions. According to the data on the background of respondents, both males and females are 75 and they are between the ages of 10 to 20, although those of 16-20. 54% of the respondents use smartphones while the others access them with their friend's phones. The study therefore concludes that secondary school students frequently use social media in their daily activities, as they spend so much time accessing the different social media accounts they have. The reason secondary school students access social media is mainly for socialization and most time they are exposed to negative immoral content such as nude videos and pictures and their friends' posts influence them to like social media content. Which influences their moral values and group norms.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The study after the field data and analysis, recommended the following.

1. The heavy usage of social media by secondary school students in Delta State should be discouraged as their parents should ensure they monitor the contents of the social media secondary school students in Delta State access.
2. Posting of sexual content on social media should be discouraged and secondary school students in Delta State should be taught how to block users who frequently nude pictures and video
3. Parents should restructure the time at which secondary school students in Delta State access social media.
4. Religious leaders should preach against unlawful activities on social media by secondary school students in Delta State.

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